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‘Quo Vadis’ Engineering Education?

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ABSTRACT

During the 46 years of SEFI's existence things have changed both in engineering practice, e.g. CAD/M and simulation, and in education, e.g. blended learning and MOOCs. However, there are some things that continue to be of concern, such as the expanding curriculum, engineering status in society, engineers' knowledge of the wider constraints affecting engineering decisions and the ability to communicate effectively to non-specialists. This has been brought into focus by the recently announced decision in the UK to establish a new university – the London Interdisciplinary School - with the expressed intention of providing a much broader curriculum of science, arts and design technology while at the same time receiving endorsement from several organisations that state they want 'a new style of graduate, who is more rounded and able to solve problems'. Knowing how much effort engineering academics make to produce a balanced curriculum, matching an understanding of basic principles with learning to address contemporary challenges, one wonders where the shortfalls exist. At the same time engineering educators are being asked to address sustainability and climate change issues, ethical dimensions, attractiveness whilst encouraging entrepreneurship. Where should we put our goals and ambitions? What is the role of lifelong learning? In this paper we try to inject clarity into the discussion by suggesting that the admission requirements of the students, the nature of the education, and the possible ongoing opportunities should be made more explicit. It is examined both from societal needs and issues bothering the profession.

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1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Starting point

The complexity of challenges facing engineers today has risen exponentially during the years of industrial revolutions. In the beginning scientists needed all the available information and they were creating new theories and inventions based on that. However, today no one can manage all the information available and the inventions are expected to tackle much wider aspects. How can engineering education not just follow - but enable students to acquire the skills to meet the requirements of future needs?

No degree can any more give enough competences for the whole career. The role of lifelong learning in engineering has become inevitable.

1.2 Future needs

But from where are the future needs coming? What is the role of engineering education when building the future? How can the cooperation between different disciplines be made free of boundaries? Furthermore, what is the role of Universities in the future - what and how much should be included in the different degrees - bachelor/master/doctor of engineering or technology; and what is the role of continuing education. How much does an individual need to carry responsibility and costs for acquiring and maintaining his/her on skills, what about the employers and society?

1.3 Growing and declining skills

Based on its report the "Future of Jobs Report 2018" the World Economic Forum has listed those skills, which are required to perform most jobs and has highlighted that these will have shifted remarkably by 2022. Still according to that report the amount of core skills that remain the same is expected to be about 58%. [1]

When taking a more detailed look at the skills listed in the figure 1 one can wonder how such skills are best developed. What kind of subjects need to be included directly in the curricula. Furthermore an important issue is the role of different pedagogical methods to be used. One example of this is how you teach or learn, perhaps broadly called "Emotional intelligence"?

However, an important issue is how one can learn "analytical thinking and innovation" or "technology design and programming" if "reading, writing, math and active listening" are not managed appropriately?

Fig. 1. Growing and declining skills from World Economic Forum; Future of Jobs report 2018 [1]

2 CHANGING WORLD

2.1 Challenges of the planet

Climate change and the problems that are caused by it can no longer be ignored. Facts and figures related to climate change are collected by The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change which is the United Nations body for assessing the science related to climate change [2]. All future decisions need to take into account a wide range of aspects that are not directly technical. Additionally the earlier constructions need rethinking and transformed to the use of sustainable solutions. Less polluting energy production, less energy consumption in the processes etc. This means that there needs to be a deep understanding and a willingness of engineers to evaluate their designs with these aspects in mind.

2.2 Challenges of the industrial work

The 4th industrial revolution is highlighting the role of artificial intelligence, internet of things and other consequences of digitalisation. These aspects are changing the way of working. As has been written by Professor Klaus Schwab, Founder and Executive Chairman of the World Economic Forum, “Ubiquitous, mobile supercomputing. Intelligent robots. Self-driving cars, neuro-technological brain enhancements and genetic editing. The evidence of dramatic change is all around us and it’s happening at exponential speed.” [3].

2.3 Challenges of globalisation

Everything seems to have a global impact. The 4th industrial revolution leads to Globalisation 4.0, combining the major shifts underway in technology geopolitics and society [4]. The financial crises and trade war, population movements, relationships

between countries and continents are all part of the environment where the future engineers work. Still, what is the role of an individual engineer? Does each engineer need a holistic view of all the impacts of their work to the global situation? Or will the needs of education lead to skills in layers where each layer needs to understand the requirements of the input of the lower level and output to the higher level. However the “layers” are not hierarchic or appreciation rankings - but all equally important.

2.4 Challenges of the pedagogical formats and the role of University

The students of today are used to flexibly combine many formats of learning. Huge amount of information is available from the internet, additionally to the organised packages of learning offered by different institutions. In many cases the need for face to face contact, tutoring, mentoring and learning physically together is considered time consuming and inefficient. However, many inventions, finding right information, ensuring the balanced consideration of the issues require “old style of guidance” additionally to the new pedagogical setups.

3 REACTIONS OF THE UNIVERSITIES

How can Universities react to these rapidly changing requirements and demands? The answers are additional to the global trends and very much dependent on cultural traditions [5]. It seems that there are several main streams to the competence development of the students:

- Deep theory with tools of STEM in a limited area of disciplines - competences of scientific work in that area
- Basic understanding of science from multiple areas (generalists), competence of defining the problem and gathering together specialists to solve it
- Pedagogical solutions might arise from theory based learning versus practise based learning. Furthermore, digital technology can be used in multidimensional online ways - materials for learning, lectures, interactive courses and even simulations of demanding technical processes.

3.1 Example from UK

Imperial College London and New Interdisciplinary School of London [6] are based on fundamentally different approaches. In both cases the most talented students are wanted. In Imperial College the accumulation of a reputation over many years attracts high quality applicants and the institution can select “the best of the best” for their programmes. Also the students are expected to work hard and learn the theories so that they can use and further develop their own in the future. In that curricula the demand for new elements to be added is ever growing - although one could think it is a narrow area. Currently however the institution is undertaking a complete review of its curricula in all departments.

On the other hand the New Interdisciplinary School of London is attracting students by promising “the needed core knowledge from each of the disciplines defined by the most successful industrialists and scientists”. Such students need to have an extraordinary talent for combining the essential knowledge without going-in too deeply on details. One can wonder, what is the real profession from this programme? How the highly intelligent graduates of these two different lines can work together, appreciate each other and create our future academic will have to be seen! **3.2**

Example from Finland

A similar type of diversity in the programmes can be recognised in Finland as well, although such extremes do not exist. In Finland the “normal” talent can enter the university and the theoretical programmes are slightly more general and the general programmes slightly more focused than in these examples from London.

The master’s programmes of Electrical Engineering are very deeply based on understanding of the calculations of electromagnetic fields and such knowledge of mathematics and physics. On the other hand there are several master’s programmes in engineering such as “Information networks” that for instance concentrate on building bridges between the machine designers and different users or customers. Analysing the challenges, creating solutions and understanding the possibilities of coding as a tool is very important. Still both of these programmes are strictly engineering programmes.

3.3 Role of continuing education

On the job learning is considered to be the most effective way of developing competences in working life. Recognising the learning and collecting a portfolio of development could help engineers to make visible the level of knowhow attained. However, additionally different kind of courses are needed. Especially in the cases when the jobs are changing, or engineers have been away from the working life for a while.

The International Association for Continuing Engineering Education IACEE is supporting and enhancing Lifelong Engineering Education around the globe for instance by promoting the use of online webinars, MOOCs and different options for learning more about sustainable development with the programme SERINA [7]

4 WHAT ATTRACTS STUDENTS

According to the authors’ experience, different types of engineers are needed. Important to all of them is to understand the role of their expertise. The usefulness of deep knowledge from narrow area needs to be introduced to colleagues who might not understand the details but who could be able to use the results.

The ones who might understand the need for a medical device might not understand how to create it - and the one to create it needs to get the information about the human

interface to produce an appropriately adaptable design. And perhaps the programmer needs only some of the information to be able to create the algorithms and coding.

The jointly needed competence is communication, appreciation of each other's orientation to contribute to the overall solution.

4.1 TEK annual survey of new graduates

Academic Engineers and Architects in Finland TEK is executing an annual feedback survey for M.Sc.(Tech) graduates [8]. The survey covers the whole country and the response rate at over 80% is amazingly high. In the year 2018 at the time of graduation 76% were already employed, and thus had some understanding of the realities of working life and competences needed. Almost 90% of the graduates answered that if they needed to choose now the area of studies they would choose engineering again.[8]

In the survey, among other things, it was asked about the different competences - how important the engineers found them, how much the competences were developed during the studies and how much they were developed while working during the study time. In the figure 2 is illustrated the results of these questions. Replies were received from a total of 1783 graduates.

Fig. 2. The evaluated importance of competences (blue line) versus the gained competences from studies (red line) and work experience (grey line), the scale of importance is: 1=Not at all (important), 2=Very little, 3=Little, 4=Somewhat, 5=Much,

6=Very much. The illustration by Arttu Piri from the 2018 survey undertaken by TEK, in Finland [8]

Of interest is that the “knowhow of own field” was evaluated very important and the competency in that was gained very well both in studies and work-experience. That confirms the need to have a deep understanding of “hard skills” and then to support those with “soft skills”. As a surprise “entrepreneurial capacities”, “basics of business operations” and “sustainable development” were ranked about as low as “knowledge of the history and development of own field”. However, in these competences even the low needed level was not reached.

Quite large gaps between the required competences and gained competences were in ethics, creativity, leadership and “digitalisation and utilisation of data” were found. The last one might be a problem for the future career if the World Economic Forum outcomes are to be believed.

4.2 ASTEP2030

An ERASMUS+ project “Attracting diverSe Talent to Engineering Profession 2030” is aiming to increase awareness of Engineering in Europe, highlighting the critical part that Engineers will play in solving global challenges and encouraging more diverse students to engage with engineering studies. That project is created by the SEFI working group of Attractiveness of Engineering Education [9].

Already the first results show that the big questions, problems and global challenges need engineering knowledge to be adapted to all developments and solutions. More cross disciplinary cooperation and diversity in all possible meanings (gender, nation, religion, region, age etc) need to be involved to build the future of human kind.

The challenge to Universities is to introduce engineering programmes as ways to become problem solvers. This means also the development on learning methods. Learning needs to be fun. Connection to real life projects, problem based learning, CDIO, use of offerings from internet like MOOC’s could enable individual learning baths.

Engineers, as a profession need to manage the “hard skills” and fundamentals to development them - furthermore communication and cooperation with other professions with honest appreciation is crucial.

5 SUMMARY

The answer to the question: ‘To where engineering education is going?’ is very much giving directions where the whole globe is going to. How well we can educate narrow deep specialist and wide generalists who can work together benefitting the competences of each other of them. Communicating and appreciating the different views. Finding solutions which are good for the sustainable development of the future.

These are not easy demands for engineering education of the future - but if engineering schools are able to manage the diversity they will attract much wider population to the profession.

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